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A STUDY OF SOCIAL IMPACT OF REALITY SHOWS ON YOUTH IN NORTHWEST MUMBAI

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INTRODUCTION:

After 1992 when our economy was liberalised and went global, that was the need of the hour, but it also exposed us to outside world, their culture, foods, way of living and even information through communication etc. one such thing that India witnessed in the process of liberalisation was satellite television and end number of foreign channels, their shows and foreign movies that were full of abusive language ,filthy words, partial or full nudity etc but it also got us opportunity to gel with knowledge about the world, regions, professionalism, technology, and most of all their stress busters shows which were based on real life character and events, that's how reality shows came into existence which provided the working class an opportunity to reflect themselves through such shows, but India and its environment are different from outside world as we are having different cultures and religion which are base of human development and generation of good values like respect for parents and elders, teachers, environment, tolerance towards other religion etc.

Post modernism is a movement of information arising out of many ideas from the elements of modernism, individuals who understand this concept either thinks differently about the transmission of information and its meaning or that this modern thoughts has flaws in consuming knowledge in an era of economic and technological, had given rise to a decentralised media dominated society.(allan, H tumner, Kenneth, jonathaan, turner, jonathan H, 2000), in other words the ideas which are having cross border representations with no real original, also unstable subjective source of communication and its due to globalisation that has resulted in innovations in communication, manufacturing and transportation.

Today's modern life is the result of globalization which has connected various culture and interconnected in such a way that it has become a global village, the post modern view is that it stresses more on subjective knowledge rather objective knowledge that leads to conditions of dissemination that alters the relationship between observer and the observed also those who consume and those who produce and truly speaking these are not positive sign, these ideals are the result of particular economic and social conditions probably that led to capitalism and it boosted the growth of broadcasting media.(larxer,steven,2008) (petrov,igor,2003).

Recent trend after year 2000 , we see bumper increase in number of channels and number of shows where evolution of women facet were given more dominance whether she is mother in law, daughter in law, love, wife, friend etc but in urban areas where people have to work for more than 14 to 16 hours a day cannot just survive on fiction shows, this tension led to ground feats for reality shows in India, it was channel v who started singing shows like viva which gave us our first girl band, it wasn't as such that this was first reality show, shows on door darshan like meri awaz suno, tol mol ke bol, etc but nobody knew it as a reality show , it was only evident when competition begin stiff and every channel wanted to look different and reach its viewers in different way, gave existence to the word reality show.

But to meet the competition and to get T.R.P, our Indian channels blindly copied the concepts from their foreign reality shows counterpart, as producer believed to put in money on those format which had good beginning in some other country but forgetting to project original unscripted ideas, it led to scripted and subjective only to get attention of the viewers, some was good for the society but some had detrimental effects on our society specifically on youth.

Infinite ways are there that could resist social constraints but it will lead to an infinite number of outcomes thus creating negative and grey areas, the author also adds that these outcomes always rely on the forms from which they spring. The viewers builds a new world upon the existing one which either takes the consumer away from the real situation or the producer creates such situation where the viewer gets inclined towards his informative area.(unger, Roberto, 2004)

In this part of research, i want to study the social impact of Indian reality on our youth in my area of study i.e (north west Mumbai).

To understand this paper 3 things should be understood properly

1. For better understanding lets understand what is society?

Society is an environment which includes living and non living factors.

In other words a mix of nature made and manmade factors.

2. Then what is social impact?

Any impact that enhances or degrade the value of living or non living factors in such a way that its existence in future is either appreciated or at vulnerability.

3. What is reality shows?

Reality television is a [genre](#) of [television programming](#) that has unscripted situations , actual occurrences, and often has unknown cast. The genre often highlights personal drama and conflict between the contestants.

To understand it better we should know different social theories and see how reality shows have those theories as a base or use in their show.

1. **Symbolic interaction theory:** this theory is also called symbolic interactionism or interaction perspective theory where people develop and rely upon different situation in the process of social interaction. (macionis, john J, 2012)

In reality shows too people and audience or viewer votes for the favourite contestants on the basis of this symbolic interaction after viewing their episodes or if we want to identify sunil pal then better is we recall his good act of a drunkard giving pravachan in a satsang “ bhakt jano, kaise ho saalo”

2. **Conflict theory:** conflict theory is all about domination in a group or community reflected in a society, social order in society is maintained by those dominated groups who represents greatest political, economic, and social resources. (macionis, john J ,2010)

This theory is well shown in shows like crime patrol where nations resources is badly exploited by political class or dominated class or in shows like roadies where people have clash of ideologies as well as they have to work as a team and increase money for the team, also criticizing the acts of contestants.

3. **Feminist theories:** this theory looks into the status of female and men in society only to understand how they interact to make women’s status a positive one, this theory talks of how women fights and raise their voice for the well being of whole women hood as whole. (hird, myraJ , 2003) (macionis, john J ,2010)

Reality shows like halla bol and emotional atyachar or webbed is such a show where women is oppressed or suppressed but it also highlights about how they have struggled and make their way and mark their name in society.

4. **Critical theory:** critical theory talks about criticizing and changing society and prevailing culture as a whole. This theory uncovers the various assumptions and provides us right picture of what people thinks.(macionis, john J ,2010)

Reality shows like sachh ka saamna and big boss are one such shows which is based on people criticizing every body’ behaviour or jhalak or nachh baliye where judge feel pride in correcting the mistakes done by contestants.

5. **Labelling theory:** this theory helps us to understand criminal behaviour and society’s reaction to a person’s specific behaviour, this theory help the centre formulate good laws that stops these criminal activities and behaviour. (macionis, john J ,2010)

Reality shows like crime petrol and savdhan India depicts different crimes done in a different way thus able to understand the behaviours of the criminals.

6. **Social learning theory:** this is a theory of individual learning phase, observational behaviour and its activity formation, and the influence of society in socializing individuals. (macionis, john J ,2012)

Reality shows are made on different themes and genres that involves people to vote for them, sms them, watch the repeat telecast of the missed episodes of his / her reality shows, post a status on social networking sites.

7. **Structural strain theory:** Robert k. Merton developed this theory and measure the tensions that are caused due to inefficiency between goals and means to achieve those goals.(macionis, john J ,2012)

Reality shows like Indian idol and dance India dance shows different genres of music and dance and masters who help these contestants to perform beautifully on the stage.

8. **Rational choice theory:** this theory projects that every human being is motivated by money and possibility of making profit, calculation of less on decision and more on benefits of the action does matter most. (amartya sen, 2008)

Reality shows too provide contestants a platform where they perform their talents and achieve fame as well as awards and prizes.

9. **Game theory:** game theory is a study of strategic decision making in a social interaction t where by the name itself gives a hint that interaction based on winning or loosing and behaviours to achieve them, it could be good and rationale achievement or other way. (Vernon.l. smith, 1992))

Shows like big boss, khatron ke khiladi, master chef and many talent shows predicts such social interactions.

10. **Social exchange theory:** this theory deals with winning or losing when he or she is made spent time with each other. (gerber, macionis,linda M, john J, 2010) Examples couples dating each other will experience whether his or her partner is cheating on him or her

Reality shows like splitsvilla and emotional atyachar deals with these type of idea and concept where youth minds are definitely attracted to such shows

11. **Thomas theorem:** Thomas theorem are those situation which depicts real scenario and consequences, it gives us an idea that real situation that a person construct throught out interaction has a real consequences whether good or bad in future.(patricia, martin, barry, 1986).

Reality shows like k.b.c, Indian idol, sare gama pa etc are such shows where people's dream is fulfilled and some where many people who struggled in their life have a say in these reality show, they either triumph or get doomed in the society as an unknown face.

12. **Control theory:** developed by travis hirschi states that a weak role played by society in its moral and values influences individuals to defy social norms and adopt behaviour that are deviant in nature. (gerber,macionis,linda M, john J, 2010)

Reality shows like satya mev jayete is based on the concept that highlight the ills happening in the society and take measures that are deviant from the system of the country.

We have to see whether our youth are exposed to these reality shows in a good way or bad way.

Let's see the argument in favour of reality shows or against it.

Arguments in favour of:

1. **Unearthing of vast talent in India:** talent based shows like kaun banega crorepati, india's got talent, the great Indian laughter challenge, Indian idol, master chef, entertainment ke liye kuchh bhi karega, x factor,dance india dance, boogie woogie etc tap those people who have been denied in their life and give them a platform to show their talent and prove their worthiness and existence not only to family but entire world.

Example:

Who could have thought that this enthusiastic bubbly girl would make impossible thing very possible in her own way , full of energy and has become talk of the town, So much so that right from Bollywood

personalities Salman Khan, aishwarya rai, Katrina kaif, mallika arora khan have taken notice and complimented and appreciated the courage and talent of this chirpy girl Shubhreet Kaur Ghumman(27), who belongs to rural Punjab. Any handicap after a fatal accident and series of failed treatments leading to amputation of a leg, could have changed the life of any common man but personal tragedies didn't dampen the spirits and motivation of Shubhreet. Not learnt to give up, the girl started her real life afresh and achieved unthinkable. She is one leg dancer Shubhreet Kaur Ghumman, native of small village Jhunda in district Sangrur, who due to her vivid dances with only one leg has touched millions of Indian heart and became the darling of thousands of TV viewers. Her performance at India's got talent being aired at a TV channel changed all for her and now she is getting many takers.

NOTE: source: the times of India , neel kamal, april 19 2014.

2. **Equal opportunity to participate:** don't know about other countries but in India where person identity is determined on the basis of religion, sex, caste, rich, poor etc, reality show proves to be a boon to people in India and these people gets equal opportunity not only to vote but also to participate and perform and even achieve their dreams.

example:

Prince group winning India's got talent season 1

Two of its members are suffering from polio. Most of the others hail from humble backgrounds and have worked as labourers in farms and construction site to earn their livelihood. But when they dance, even the best in business cannot match.

Note: Mishra, sandeep, the times of india, 16 aug 2009

3. **Film stars on television:** In India, celebrities like rajnikanth, amitabh bachhan, shahrukh khaan, aamir khan, salmaan khan etc are given the status of god and that's why people die to have one glimpse or photograph or autograph, therefore to cash in the popularity of these stars, the reality shows started having celebrity as a judge, as an anchor, or as a participants. Indirectly common man do not have to shelve out money to have glimpse of these celebrities as they will be coming every day or in weekends on television itself, some reality show to have good trp even provide offers to talk to their favourite celebrity.

Example:

1. Big boss hosted by salman khan
2. Indian idol judge annu malik, vishal dadlaani, shreya ghosal
3. K.b.c hosted by amitabh bachhan
4. Dus ka dum hosted by salmaan khan
5. Satya mev jayte hosted by aamir khan
6. India's got talent judged by karan johar, mallika arora, kiran kherr.
7. Entertainment ke liye kuchh bhi karega judged by farah khan and annu mallik
8. Dance india dance judged by mithun chakravarty
9. Roadies anchored by raghu raam.

- 4. Raising of social issues of society:** now a days reality show not only provide a second view of the people but also how they live their life through social evils facing the society. Social issues like female foeticide, acid attack, rape, corruption, farmers suicide, police stress way of life, youth problem etc are highlighted through reality shows. Shows like k.b.c, satya mev jayate, halla boll, emotional attyachar etc comes up with these social evils with a **solution**.

Example:

1. This reality show from satya mev jayte discussing on a social issue and inspiring many people.

Bollywood actor Aamir Khan's philanthropic television venture 'Satyamev Jayate 2' came to an end on Sunday (March 30 2014) after 5 episodes.

The episodes talked about fighting rape, police, garbage and hygiene conditions, corruption and ended with a bang giving its take on the importance of voting.

[\(http://indianexpress.com/article/entertainment/television/aamir-khans-satyamev-jayate-season-2-finale-talks-about-elections-2014/\)](http://indianexpress.com/article/entertainment/television/aamir-khans-satyamev-jayate-season-2-finale-talks-about-elections-2014/) 30 march 2014.

2. One reality show named halla boll which tells us about women in different life situations were exposed to physical or sexual harrasement and how did they come back strongly and opposed those people.

5. Reality shows makes common man a star overnight:

The main mantra of reality shows in india is that they have been able to connect with the common man of this country and allows them to show their talents and feel blessed with their existence.

Abhijit sawant, winner of Indian idol season one, sunil paal, winner of the great Indian laughter challenge and also who can forget harshwardhan nawathe, our first crorepati from first season of kbc and many other winners from reality shows are common people and overnight they were loved and recognised my millions.

6. **Changed the perception of Indian audiences:** it wasn't easy to change the mindset of Indians who were busy engaged in melodrama of ekta Kapoor serials like saas bhi kabhi bahu thi, kahaani ghar ghar ki, kasauti zindagi ki, kussum etc on different serials, people needed a change specially youth who wanted for themselves a show that would express their feeling, something new and out of the box ideas and then came shows like viva on channel v, boggie woogie on sony and kbc that too on sony. Now Indian audience had an option to make their mood fresh by tuning into reality shows and feel expressed through shows like antakshri and saare gama pa.
7. **Good source of entertainment:** what sets apart a reality show from other fiction and scripted shows is their surprise package, a package of competitiveness, friendship, emotion, growth history of the contestants, music, celebrity anchor or judge or participants add value to the watching of the audience which make them glued to the t.v thus reality shows are good source of entertainment.

Example: on the day 15 august prince group from India's got talent season first , in a semi final, depicted Indian flag in their act which hooked the audience and they were so involved in the act that they started chanting " bharat maata ki jai"

Source : princdancegroup.in.....acts

8. **Promotion of serial, films and different brand:** reality shows is a place where audience are hooked to, is an added advantage to show producers as increase in trp will definitely attract movie makers to small screen to promote their movies and in this way even audiences will also get a glimpse of their favourite actor or actresses on small screen apart from watching them on big screen.

Example: a popular reality show comedy nights with kapil is bombarded with many film producer with their star cast and interact with the audience and thus promoting their film on the show, akshay kumar for boss, shahrukh khan for Chennai express, salmaan khan for jai ho, shushant singh rajput and pariniti chopra for sudhh desi romance, madhuri dixit and juhi chawl for gulaabi gang etc have come on the show and made their presence felt to the audience by dancing with or singing with them.

Its not that only films get promoted, if any reality show is a hit at a particular prime time, it paves way for the new serial launch and its all done due to the popularity of reality show.

Even brand like Vodafone associating themselves with big boss allowing Vodafone customer to call and ask any of the contestants about the behaviour in the show.

9. **Acknowledgement of achievement:** reality shows not only give a platform to young and old dynamic people but it also acknowledges their talents and breed them, harness it to become better and better.

Example : india's got talent winner

Season 1: prince group, berhampur, Orissa

Season 2: shilling chamber choir, shilling, Meghalaya

Season 3: the suresh and Vernon group,

Season 4: young dancers sonali majumdar and maraju sumanth from kokatta

Season5: ragini makkhar and naadyog kathak dancer group from indore.

Source : color channel.

The winners above is declared winner only when the judges and viewers have acknowledged their achievements, talents etc and hence they are loved for their work.

10. **Publicity of some regions:** the regions which were not least importance were never given weightage in our view, but thanks to reality shows like rakhi ka swayamvar where whole rajasthan's Udaipur fort was put to light or judges going to different place like delhi, Mumbai, pune, etc for different auditions do highlight the specialities of those areas. Or shows like high way on plate where rocky and andy explore various dhabas across the countries is a perfect way of giving publicity to the area or region.

Source: Udaipur to host rakhi ka swayamvar , tnn, jun11, 2009,12.00am ist..

11. **prizes and reward:** reality shows attract many people not only because of its uniqueness but also due to cash and reward being offered to the winning contestants.

Even in Maslow theory of motivation, accordingly mentions that in self actualisation theory, it is evident that a person will thrive to achieve something unique in his life.

12. **Revenue generation:** for anybody who thinks reality show is a costly affair then they are right, it is high hefty reality shows but look at the positive side they are able to attract many people not only in India but in abroad plus they vote for their favourite contestants, watch their videos on mobile, share them on social networking site, and many other activities, thus it is able to generate huge revenue not only to mobile service providers but also to channels in terms of advertisement revenue, and taxes collected by government through these providers and channels are used for the development of the regions and employment creation.
13. **Knowledge of the world:** it is due to reality shows that we sitting in a four square wall have been able to witness the different culture and traditions happening in and around the world. Reality shows target this aspect of human sense where they feel to know more about those surroundings like if we see master chef India or Australia, we come to know various recipes of different countries, in k.b.c, the questions comprises of not only Indian but it covers all aspects of the world like geography, world history, science, medicine etc.

So according to j. Peter denny and john g.benjafield (1968) that an information or a concept or their instances can be interpreted in either a positive way or negative.

So if we take the positive of reality show in a good ways the same instances could be interpreted in a negative way too.

Lets see the negative side of reality show or argument against relity shows

1. **Reality shows doesn't portray reality:** the first and foremost argument against reality shows is that they are rigged, biased, and influenced by judges personal favourites. They are timed in such a way that it creates series of emotion, drama, and trp for the producers.

E.g like rakhi ka swayamvar, mere khwaabo ki mallika, roadies and many adventure reality reality shows are made in a documentary manner therefore to place authenticity on such show is ridiculous.

2. **religion and community targets:** many of the reality shows like talents shows pick contestants from all walks of life, caste creed or sex and less priority on talents, only to attract their religion and community votes that will increase not only the trp but also business.

e.g : a reality show called big brother, u.k when planned to rope shilpa shetty in the show, only to attract asian origin of people towards the show and when she was surrounded by racial abuse by the inmates, it gave the channel hugh trp and also sympathy towards racial abuse person and apathy towards asian community.

3. **setting a bad example for youth:** many reality shows gets those contestants who have been denied or objected or fell into controversy, only to get attention of the viewers, thus very few reality show takes morality of their show.

e.g: reality show like "jhalak" in its new season has shreeshant as its contestants who have been sacked by bcci and matter is in court but involving him as a contestants will definitely catch the eyes of the viewer but a wrong message will be sent to the youth of this country that in spite doing unlawful things, people are enjoying their life.

4. **develops wrong notation among people:** reality shows in the name of portraying real things sometimes sends wrong signals to the society, i like to point it out that what people takes information, it

is they who bifurcate into wrong or right notation, and many a time especially youth who takes the negative way.

e.g: shows like crime petrol, emotional atychhhar, savdhan india should be given parental guidance tag as the content in these shows require some elder people interpreting those message portraying out of those shows, otherwise todays youth will be misguided to do wrong things and ruin his life and become a nuisance in society.

5.exposure: when some of Indian reality makers of talents shows where contestants of ages below 12 years are thrown against each other and that too to compete at an tender young age will expose the child to social evils like psychology problem, depression, coping up with fame and maintaining it etc

6. wastage of productive time: the reality show deviates the youth mentality from academics to success and popularity by means of short cut.

e.g : shows like junior master chef, desh ke hunnar baaj, dance India dance little juniors, these concepts have made the kids think apart from academics and sports, but truly speaking it only attracts those who have these talents but others kids who doesn't have, dream and waste years to get on the stage of reality shows.

7. aggressive behaviour like abusive language, fight, anger etc: in order to glorify the shows and make it spicy, plus to increase the t.r.p, the producer of the shows go to any extent to poke contestants use aggression, cat fights, use of abusive language , display of anger etc to directly or indirectly promote its shows.

e.g : shows like big boss, roadies, emotional attyachar etc are such shows which are not good for watching and that too audience under the age of 18 years.

8. humiliation as an entertainment: many of the talents shows during the audition round do make fun of those who are not good in projecting their talent properly but people love to enjoy watching those contestants humiliated by judges.

According to Thomas theory, the author patricia and barry points those situation which depicts real scenario and consequences, it gives us an idea that real situation that a person who is viewing constructs in such a waythat interaction has a real consequences whether good or bad in future.(patricia, martin, barry, 1986).

This is true others criticism is enjoyed by others in our society.

e.g : shows like Indian idol, dance india dance, roadies,etc humiliate people to create trp for their shows.

9. psychological disorder like low self esteem, frustration, depression, stealing, celebrity imitation etc: the contestants who give auditions and then gets rejected goes through psychological disorder like low esteem, depression or some time they imitate some celebrity to get rid of their low conscious appeal among people.

e.g : shows like rakhi ka insaaf hosted by bollywood celebrity rakhi sawant humiliate one man on the show who fought with his wife, he was badly humiliated that resulted man committing suicide.

10. source of voyeurism: many of the reality shows rather promoting reality, they are promoting voyeurism in the name of reality thus attracting innocent adolescent kids to wonder with their age curiosity with such shows to get their queries solved

e.g : shows like big boss contestants like Pamela Anderson wearing blouse that exposed her breast and contestants like sunny leone entering with a porn star tag in the show only to increase the likes of the show but in reality its promoting voyeurism as a whole.

It is also to see what our newspaper media thinks about Indian reality shows, lets see their point of view.

1. **One legged dancer:** Who could have thought that this enthusiastic bubbly girl would make impossible thing very possible in her own way , full of energy and has become talk of the town, So much so that right from Bollywood personalities Salman Khan,aishwarya rai, Katrina kaif, mallaika arora khan have taken notice and complimented and appreciated the courage and talent of this chirpy girl Shubhreet Kaur Ghumman(27), who belongs to rural Punjab. Any handicap after a fatal accident and series of failed treatments leading to amputation of a leg, could have changed the life of any common man but personal tragedies didnt dampen the spirits and motivation of Shubhreet. Not learnt to give up, the girl started her real life afresh and achieved unthinkable. She is one leg dancer Shubhreet Kaur Ghumman, native of small village Jhunda in district Sangrur, who due to her vivid dances with only one leg has touched millions of Indian heart and became the darling of thousands of TV viewers. Her performance at India' got talent being aired at a TV channel changed all for her and now she is getting many takers.

NOTE: source: the times of india , neel kamal, feb 3 2014.

(timesofindia.indiatimes.com/entertainment/Punjabi/movies/news-interviews/the-one-legged-dancer-getting-kudos-from-salman-khan/articleshow/29817301.cms)

2. **Limerick man:** this article talks about a man nam gautam sen gupta, aresident of mall road near dum dum in kolkatta,who has taken v.r.s from his private job and works as an insurance agent, not ending here,he writes limericks (chara) highlighting the evils of reality shows on t.v channels and recite at many cultural functions.you can call him a crusader who puts words and give a voice against many social evils of reality shows which not only spoiled our society but our today's youth too. Mr. Sen gupta wouldn't have taken this step unless he saw a young becoming a mental wreck after participating in a reality show and through his limerick, he gives message to various parents to control this at the advent of reality shows.

By sabya sachi bandopadhyay for Indian express, sun, 17 june 2012.

(archive.indianexpress.com/news/limerick-man/962901)

3. **Prince group winning India's got talent season 1:**

Two of its members are suffering from polio. Most of the others hail from humble backgrounds and have worked as labourers in farms and construction site to earn their livelihood. But when they dance, nobody would be able to match their step.

Note. Indian express news service,23 august 2009

(newindianexpress.com/states/odhisa/article73554.ece?service=print)

4. **Man's murder comes to light after wife's confession on t.v reality show:**

This article appearing in the times of india, covering an article which mention about an incident that happened on a reality tv show set which shocked not only Chennai but entire world, a wife name baby kala confessed on Indian tv reality show of killing her 39 year old husband with the help of her lover gowri Shankar as her husband was a biggest hindrance to their affairs.

By sindhu kannan, tnn, april 30, 2014, the times of India

(timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/mans-murder-comes-to-light-after-wifes-confession-0n-tv-reality-show/articleshow/34422135.cms).

5. **This reality show from satya mev jayte discussing on a social issue and inspiring many people.**

Bollywood actor Aamir Khan's philanthropic television venture 'Satyamev Jayate 2' came to an end on Sunday (March 30 2014) after 5 episodes.

The episodes talked about fighting rape, police, garbage and hygiene conditions, corruption and ended with a bang giving its take on the importance of voting.

(<http://indianexpress.com/article/entertainment/television/aamir-khans-satyamev-jayate-season-2-finale-talks-about-elections-2014/>) 30 march 2014.

6. **Reality shows give exposure:** this is an interview taken by kavita awasthi, a hindustan times reporter with tv actor kritika karma (kuchh toh log kahenge fame) talking about participating in a celebrity dance show " jhalak" as the rality show will provide her maximum exposure.

(by kavita awasthi, Hindustan times jaipur,wed 21 may 2014. (paper.hindustantimes.com/epaper/iphone/homepage.aspx#_article4e8cbd9f-ec2e-47cb-b5c9-c3d921a07a58)

(<http://paper.hindustantimes.com/epaper/viewer.aspx>)

7. **Sunny leone to host dating reality show splitsvilla:** this article talks about pornstar turned bollywood actress sunny leone to host a reality show called splitsvilla,a show which revolves around young boys and girls do things to secure a place in a villa, basically it is ' hunt for a love' show where contestants do tasks to stay in competition and mingle to woo love of opposite sex in the villa.

Hindustan times,pti, Mumbai,april 14 2014).

(<http://www.hindustantimes.com/entertainment/television/sunny-leone-to-host-dating-reality-show-splitsvilla/article1-1207999.aspx>).

8. **Vote machine stardom:** this article talks about Indian idol season 1 finale contestant abhijeet sawant, on his experience of instant fame on reaching to finale after audience vote plus judging by celebrity panel,this article not only talks about 1 cr recording contract and serious stardom but also people interaction on social networking site as well as through votes.

Outlook magazine feb 28, 2005 by saumya roy

(outlookindia.com/article/vote-machine-stardom/226633)

9. **What young think about reality tv shows:** the article talks about how reality shows has been able to tap young mind by exploiting the element of unpredictability. It also talked about

how reality shows participants are exact representation of hyperbole temperament of youth, shows like k.b.c and axe your ex are such shows which highlights relationships and competition and it forms a central ideas of any reality show.it also talked about how viewers find themselves with the level of identification with the characters on reality shows which attracts sponsors, it talked about how now a days reality show has become a lucrative career and instant success to fame and how youth's interest is attracted by shows related to peers group and with theme like love life.

By economic times bureau October 27, 2010.

http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2010-10-27/news/27616980_1_reality-show-emotional-atyachaar-characters).

10. **India restricts ' adult content' day time reality show:** this news discussed how Indian government was sensitive towards adult content shown on few reality shows and how they they banned Indian reality show ' big boss' to show adult content during day time and even went ahead to tell them to telecast their show between 11.00pm to 5.am slot. The government was forced to take decision after announcement of bay watch star Pamela Anderson in to the big boss house.

By bbc news south Asia, 17 nov2010

(bbc.co.uk/news/world-south-asia-11777477)

11. **Indian reality tv shows goes wrong:** the article talked about a contestant anjar khan 22 who took part in a reality show " khatron ke khiladi" (dare devils) in Indian city of indore was asked to stay under water for as long as possible but he collapsed and was declared serious.

By BBC news south Asia , 15 july 2008 u.k

(news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/south_asia/7507353.stm)

Reality show effect on society.

1. The special episode was aired on sony for k.b.c on September 13 2011 , Thursday what was so special about this kbc episode, is questions being asked was made easy, or the anchor amitabh bachhan was replaced by some other celebrity, no need to fly your horses, the special was the two women aparna mallikar (25) and manjusha ambarwar (18) the two women fighting all odds and problems, problem which was the common factor for both of them as the only earning member in their family committed suicide. This is common in draught affected areas in yavatmal district in vidarbha, where the cotton growing farmers couldn't been able to repay the loan amount and committed suicide. In case of aparna, a mother of two daughters was not even aware that her husband had taken a loan from urban bank and at the age of 25, fighting all evils, she took up farming for her feeding of daughters and manjusha who was persuing journalism degree from Nagpur university had the same instance, her father ramdas was among the first ones to kill himself for the same reason.

Aparna answered as many as six questions on the show as she cleverly used her life line and won 6.40 thousand rupees plus 50000 personally given by amitabh bachhan and still 60000 rupees debt is on her family but had to quit on the seventh question as she knew the answer but she was not sure and no life line left, before leaving the show she was determined to offer help to 13000 widows living miserably after their husbands took extreme step to get rid of mounting debts and crop failures.

She was recommended by vidharba jan andolan samiti president kishor tiwari who was being approached by sony executives to raise different issues related to society through k.b.c.

(<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/nagpur/Vidarbha-farmers-widow-wins-Rs-6-4L-in-KBC/articleshow/9966036.cms>)

2. A seventeen year old girl name sonali mukherjee, beautiful, intelligent, ambitious young woman, who wanted to excel in her studies, had a dream of achieving phd in sociology and coming from poor background, have seen her family struggle for even small things, her father being a security gaurd in the state of Jharkhand suddenly sees her herself in all mess, she lost her ability to talk, see, eat, hear and even walk. How suddenly a girl lose everything even her grandfather died grasping the trauma, and her mother went into depression.

How the plight of this girl and father came into lime light, yes through reality show and that too audience favourite “ kaun banega crorepati “, a foreign version of “ who wants to be a millionaire”.

On the set of k.b.c in year 2012 and that too in presence of her favourite actor and household name celebrity amitabh bachhan, she revealed her trauma and how she was acid attacked by three college class mate and how she lost her body parts in that acid attack in 2003, that was not ending , her father had to sell and wind up the businesses, recovered all money and spent on his daughter’s surgery and all in all 27 times she had to go through knife i.e. surgery. She came on the show won 40000 \$ i.e 25 lakhs rupees and also told how and what type of treatment this law provide to Indian women as still those men were freed after two years of jail and when appeal in higher court, no dates have been given yet , now after winning the amount she is planning to go to delhi and get the best treat ment for her.

(edition.cnn.com/2013/05/21/world/asia/india-acid-attack/index.html)

3. A reality show “ satyamev jayate” anchored by bollywood actor amir khan in season 2, a show highlighting social issues, the very second episode telecasted the problems faced by rape victim and highlighted that they not only go through pain due to rape but after that too they are traumatised by doctors, nurses, compounders, policemen and our country’s weak law.

The effect of this episode was tremendous and the department of health research (dhr) along with Indian council of medical research (icmr) with the help of experts formulated national guidelines to all hospitals to set up a designated room for forensic and medical examination of victims plus banned two finger test done earlier to check whether the victim is really raped or not, under the strict guidelines of union health ministry. not only this, all hospitals were also said to have counselling centre to address psycho- social impact of sexual violence and reduce their woes. Also there must be provision to provide alternative clothing for the victims plus the evidences should be carefully collected in sensitive cases. as per the guidelines, medical test should not be carried out in presence of third person and a female attendant is compulsory incase the doctor is male and ordered the doctors not to use the word rape in their statements.

(<http://www.thehealthsite.com/healthcare/satyamev-jayate-impact-new-medical-guidelines-to-deal-with-sexual-assault-victims/>).

Graphical analysis :

A questionnaires were filled by working youth age between 23-30 years. And the area of study and place is infinity mall andheri west. And inorbit mall goregaon west.

Male	50
Female	50

Q.1). how often you watch television?

Always	36
Sometimes	64
Never	00

Q.2). how much hours you spent time for watching television?

1-3 hours	61
More than 3 hours	39

q.3) what types of programme you watch Rate it

	good	average	bad
1. daily serials	10	29	61
2. reality shows	30	59	11
3. music	60	33	07
4. news	17	37	46
5. movies	38	49	13
6. cartoons	10	10	80
7. animal /adventure	37	56	07

q.4) why is indian audience specially youth getting attracted towards indian televisions reality shows. (any one)

1) youth hobbies are explored through talent shows =20

2) awareness through reality shows as they high light indian social problems like unemployment, corruption,acid attack etc.=30

3) just because it is hosted by a celebrity. =50

q.5) rate the following reality shows?

reality show	very poor (1)	poor (2)	good (3)	very good (4)	excellent (5)
1. big boss	08	07	40	15	30
2. d.i.d	-	-	10	50	40
3. india's got talent	-	-	35	15	50
4. k.b.c	-	-	30	35	35
5. indian idol	-	-	40	40	20
6. jhalak	-	10	55	35	-
7. nachh baliye	35	35	20	10	-

8. satya mev jayte			15	25	60
9. coffee with karan			55	45	
10. roadies	10	10	36	44	
11. splitsvilla	14	16	48	22	
12. webbed			14	16	
13. crime petrol			32	48	
14. savdhan india			16	32	
15. emotional atyachar	30	25	10	10	

16. gumrah			32	10	
17. confession of indian teenager			22	14	
18. comedy circus		04	44	36	16
19. comedy with kapil	04	04	20	30	42
20. entertainment ke liye kuchh bhi karega	32	10	22	16	
21. gangs of hasipurr			10	12	
22. fear factor			44	56	

q.6) which shows highlight the social issues of indian society (from above).(any one)

satyamev jayate	54
k.b.c	20
crime petrol	16
savdhan india	10

q.7) which reality show highlight violence, abusive language, affairs ..sex etc..(select from above) (any one).

Big boss	43
Splitzvilla	40
Roadies	17

Findings:

- 1.** it is clearly evident that many of the respondents do not love to watch daily soap, and they prefer music, reality shows and movies over daily soap. The respondents spend more hours as a part of corporate culture around 12 hours a day, they plan trips once or twice a year but in order to compensate this they prefer animal and adventure providing channels. Today's cartoons do not attract working youth and even they prefer to stay away from news channels.
- 2.** In India, respondents prefer watching reality shows which is driven by celebrities.
- 3.** Top 5 reality shows as per respondent. (people who have ticked 'excellent')

Satyamev jayte	60
India's got talent	50
Comedy nights with kapil	42
Dance India dance	40
Kaun banega crorepati	35

- 4.** The top five reality shows are those shows which deal with talent hunt and social issues of this country like crime patrol, savdan India. It doesn't mean that people don't like other shows which have abusive language, voyeurism etc.
- 5.** Big boss and splitvilla accounts for 83% (43+40) of respondent views as shows which show vulgarity, abusive language, flirting, violence etc. Unfortunately the same respondents have given the same three shows big boss, splitvilla, roadies good response and have preferred to watch.

Big boss	85 (45+15+30)
roadies	80 (36+44)
splitvilla	70 (48+22)

The respondents love to watch adventure and voyeurism based reality shows.

- 6.** It is clear from top five reality shows that people are attracted by celebrities on reality shows.

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